

Water Activation Experiments and Simulations to support ITER operation

Luka Snoj^{1,2,*}, Domen Kotnik¹, Julijan Peric^{1,2}, Domen Govekar^{1,2}, Igor Lengar¹, Vladimir Radulović¹, Patrick Suvan³, Marco De Pietri^{3,12}, Andrea Colangeli⁴, Stefano Loreti⁴, Nicola Fonnesu⁴, Simone Noce⁴, Rosaria Villari⁴, Xavier Litaudon^{5a}, Romain Boffy^{5b}, Adrien Gruel^{5b}, Aljaž Kolšek⁶, Raul Pampin⁶, Eduardo Masia^{6b}, Francesca Cau⁶, Marco Fabbri⁶, Thomas Berry⁷, Aleksander Dubas⁷, Callum L. Grove⁷, Timothy Germany⁷, Chantal Shand⁷, Theodora Vasilopoulou⁸, Ion Evangelos Stamatelatos⁸, Axel Klix⁹, Jan Kozić^{9,14}, Toraf Doering¹⁰, Jakub Włodarczyk¹¹, Barbara Bienkowska¹¹, Ewa Łaszyńska¹³

¹ Reactor Physics Department, Jožef Stefan Institute, Slovenia

² Faculty of mathematics and physics, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia

³ Departamento de Ingeniería energética, Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia (UNED), Calle Juan del Rosal 12, Madrid 28040, Spain

⁴ ENEA, NUC Department, Via E. Fermi 45, 00044 Frascati, Rome, Italy

^{5a} CEA, F-13108 St-Paul-Lez-Durance, France

^{5b} CEA, DES, IRESNE, Department of Reactor Studies, Cadarache F-13108 Saint-Paul-Lez-Durance, France

⁶ Fusion for Energy, Josep Pla 2, Torres Diagonal Litoral B3, 08019 Barcelona, Spain

^{6b} ATG, Placa Ernest Lluc i Martin 5, Barcelona, 08019, Spain

⁷ UKAEA, Culham Campus, Abingdon, Oxfordshire, OX14 3DB, United Kingdom

⁸ National Centre for Scientific Research “Demokritos”, Institute of Nuclear and Radiological Science and Technology, Energy and Safety, 15341 Agia Paraskevi, Athens, Greece

⁹ Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Hermann-von-Helmholtz-Platz 1, 76344 Eggenstein-Leopoldshafen, Germany

¹³ Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf, Institute of Ion Beam Physics and Materials Research, Bautzner Landstrasse 400, 01328 Dresden, Germany

¹¹ Institute of Plasma Physics and Laser Microfusion, 23 Hery Street, 01-497 Warsaw, Poland

¹² MIT, Plasma Science and Fusion Center (PSFC), 77 Massachusetts Avenue, 02139 Cambridge, United States

¹³ AGH University of Krakow, Faculty of Energy and Fuels, Department of Nuclear Energy and Radiochemistry, al. A. Mickiewicza 30, 30-059 Krakow, Poland

¹⁴ Czech Technical University in Prague, Faculty of Nuclear Sciences and Physical Engineering, Department of Nuclear Reactors, V Holešovičkách 2, 180 00 Prague 8, Czech republic

* Corresponding author: luka.snoj@ijs.si

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ABSTRACT

Water is the primary coolant in most current fission reactors and is a promising option for future fusion reactors. In fusion systems, water cools in-vessel components where it is exposed to high-energy (~14 MeV) neutrons, becoming activated and producing radioactive nuclides that emit 6 MeV–7 MeV gamma rays and delayed neutrons (0.4 MeV–1.7 MeV). Predicting dose rates from activated water requires coupling computational fluid dynamics, radiation transport, and activation simulations. EUROfusion, through the Preparation of ITER Operation (WP PrIO) work package, is tackling this challenge by developing both computational tools and validation experiments. Several fluid activation codes—FLUNED, RSTM, GammaFlow, and ActiFlow—have been developed, each emphasizing specific strengths. RSTM, developed by F4E using Ansys Fluent, aligns with industrial needs. Conversely, institutions like UNED and UKAEA use the open-source OpenFOAM for flexibility and integration with research workflows. Having both proprietary and open-source solutions allows for cross-validation and scenario-based analysis. To support these efforts, the KATANA water activation loop was commissioned in 2023 at the Jožef Stefan Institute’s TRIGA Mark II reactor. KATANA offers stable, high-energy neutron and gamma fields from activated water, operating in pulse or steady-state modes with adjustable flow and an extra delayed loop. It enables detector testing, shielding studies, and benchmark experiments. In 2024, three campaigns measured neutron and gamma-ray fields using active and passive detectors: gamma spectrometers (HPGe and LaBr₃), TLDs, ³He counters, lithium-glass scintillators, and activation foils (Au, Ni, In). Gamma rays from ¹⁶N and delayed neutrons from

^{17}N were successfully detected. These experiments, along with uncertainty analyses, provide benchmarks for validating and enhancing fluid activation models.

Keywords: Water activation, KATANA, simulations, experiments, fusion, fission, radioactivity

1. INTRODUCTION

Water as a primary coolant is used in the most fission reactors today and will play an important role in the performance of fusion reactors. After being irradiated and activated, the cooling water flows through the cooling circuit, usually outside the primary biological shield surrounding the reactor vessel, and disperse the radioactivity throughout the plant. The threshold energy for the main water activation reaction, i.e. $^{16}\text{O}(n,p)^{16}\text{N}$, is about 10.5 MeV. Thus, neutrons in fusion reactors leads to water activity that is 5 orders of magnitude higher than in fission reactors of similar power [1]. In fission reactors, the fraction of the neutron spectrum exceeding the $^{16}\text{O}(n,p)^{16}\text{N}$ threshold (~ 10.5 MeV) is very small, on the order of 0.1 %, and water activation is a secondary concern adequately handled by existing operational codes. In contrast, the 14.1 MeV D-T neutrons in fusion systems are well above this threshold, making ^{16}N the dominant gamma-emitting activation product. Moreover, fusion neutron energies efficiently activate ^{17}O and ^{18}O , producing ^{17}N (a delayed-neutron emitter) and ^{19}O , creating mixed high-energy gamma and neutron fields that are not encountered in fission facilities. The resulting dose rates from activated coolant water are expected to dominate the radiation environment outside the bio-shield in ITER, making this a safety-critical issue requiring dedicated experimental validation and new computational methodologies. Numerous computational analyses of the water activation process have been carried out for ITER and DEMO. However, cooling water as a radiation source is still poorly understood due to the lack of experimental nuclear data and inconsistencies among major nuclear data libraries [2], inaccurate computational methods/codes considering time- and spatial dependent radiation sources (such as the flow of activated water in the cooling system [3]), experimental facilities to validate the methodology, and most importantly the lack of water activation experiments under fusion-relevant conditions [4].

Figure 1: Schematic flow diagram of calculational methodology.

To calculate dose rates due to activated fluid, one must first determine the neutron irradiation field in which the fluid becomes activated; that is, the spatial and energy distribution of the neutron flux must

be calculated. Next, this profile must be combined with the nuclide location and irradiation time to obtain time- and spatially-dependent reaction rates, and thus the spatial distribution of activated nuclides. The activated nuclides are then transported along the pipes, taking their decay into account. The spatial and temporal distribution of activated nuclides constitutes the source term, which is used as an input parameter for the particle transport equation. This equation is then used to calculate the temporal and spatial dose field around the pipes. The schematic diagram of this approach is depicted in Figure 1.

In order to address this challenge a task Fluid activation tools development and experiment for ITER relevant conditions was initiated under the Work package Preparation of ITER Operation (WPPrIO) within the EUROfusion consortium. The purpose of the task is to develop methodologies to calculate dose fields around activated fluid (water) and to validate them against experiments. Various types of neutron and gamma-ray detectors are used to assess the dose fields and are thoroughly described in section 3.1. Several approaches are used to develop calculational tools and are thoroughly described in section 3.2. The organization of the project and its main areas of activity are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Organisational chart.

Moreover, a closed-water activation loop, namely KATANA [5-7] was built at the end of 2023 the Jožef Stefan Institute research reactor TRIGA Mark II (JSI TRIGA) [8] in Slovenia, which serves as a well-defined and stable 6 MeV – 7 MeV gamma-ray source. Such a high-energy radiation facility allows various experiments based on water activation, e.g. shielding experiments using ITER relevant materials, investigation of the response of detectors to high-energy gamma radiation, investigation of short-lived moving radiation sources, validation of computational codes/methods, improving nuclear data, etc.

After the successful construction of the KATANA at the end of 2023 and extensive commissioning phase was initiated to determine the operational characteristics of KATANA, which provides in-depth knowledge and capabilities for its operation and, above all, serves as a basis for further, more detailed (benchmark) experiments. For this reason, several experiments, i.e. characterisation of the neutron flux inside the inner irradiation Snail, characterisation of the neutron and γ dose rate map, response to a

change in reactor power and flow rate, were performed in the period between 21 December 2023 and 16 February 2024 with a reactor core configuration #253. A comprehensive description of the performed experiments is provided in [5]. This is a review paper of the EUROfusion WP PrIO task, with KATANA serving as the central experimental facility.

Although KATANA operates with a fission neutron spectrum rather than 14.1 MeV D-T neutrons, the facility produces the same activation products relevant to fusion — ^{16}N , ^{17}N , and ^{19}O — via identical threshold reactions on oxygen isotopes. The key differences are quantitative, not qualitative: the fraction of the KATANA spectrum above the 10.5 MeV $^{16}\text{O}(n,p)^{16}\text{N}$ threshold is $\sim 0.01\%$ compared to $\sim 17\%$ at the ITER first wall, resulting in correspondingly lower specific activities ($\sim 2.8 \times 10^7$ Bq/l for ^{16}N vs. $\sim 10^{13}$ Bq/l in ITER). However, since activity scales linearly with reaction rate, the lower absolute flux does not affect the validation of the coupled CFD–activation–transport methodology, which is the primary objective. One notable difference is that thermal neutron capture on ^{18}O produces a relatively higher proportion of ^{19}O in KATANA ($\sim 14\%$ of total activity) compared to ITER ($< 0.01\%$), but this is resolved experimentally through spectroscopic decomposition of individual decay products. Hydraulically, KATANA covers turbulent flow regimes ($\text{Re} = 8 \times 10^3 - 1.1 \times 10^5$) with adjustable flow rates (0.05 l/s – 0.68 l/s), and its two-loop configuration allows independent control of irradiation and decay times. In summary, KATANA is designed as a code validation facility: it reproduces the relevant physics (activation channels, decay transport, mixed gamma-neutron fields) at experimentally accessible activity levels, enabling systematic benchmarking of the computational tools being developed for ITER operational support.

2. KATANA WATER ACTIVATION FACILITY

The KATANA water activation facility was commissioned in the “Jožef Stefan” Institute TRIGA (JSI TRIGA) research reactor hall in late 2023. It serves as a controlled source of high-energy gamma-rays (6 MeV–7 MeV) and neutrons with energies of 0.3 MeV, 1.2 MeV and 1,71 MeV. It was developed to support experimental studies of water activation phenomena and is designed with high operational flexibility. This allows its use for various purposes, including calibration of radiation detectors and dosimeters, shielding investigations, validation of simulation tools for fusion reactor cooling systems, and measurements of integral cross sections [5,6].

Figure 3. Schematic (top - left), KATANA water activation loop (top - right) and KATANA facility (bottom).

The facility features a closed water activation loop composed of three main sections: the inner section, the outer section, and the control panel, schematically illustrated in Figure 3. The inner section is installed in the Radial Piercing Port (RPP) of the JSI TRIGA reactor, where neutron interactions generate short-lived radioisotopes in the water. The activated water circulates through pipes to the outer section, which is housed within the concrete shielding next to the RPP. This section includes two circuits—one short and one extended delay loop—interconnected via a three-way valve. For the experiments discussed in this work, only the short loop was utilized due to the short half-life of the radionuclide under investigation. The activated water is continuously monitored in a measurement volume before being recirculated through the pump to the inner section. The entire system is remotely operated and controlled via the control panel situated behind the concrete shielding [6]. The main operational characteristics and diagnostics of the KATANA are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Characteristics of KATANA (JSI TRIGA)

OPERATION MODES		
Reactor	Steady state/variable	0 kW – 250 kW
	Pulse mode	10 MW – 140 MW
Water flow	Steady state/variable	0.05 L/s – 0.68 L/s
	Pump pulse	
Loop configuration	Primary - short	12.8 L
	Secondary - delay	35.5 L
	Branching - both	38.7 L
DIAGNOSTICS		
Detectors/sensors	Gamma	2 × HPGe, 2 × LaBr, 15 × TLD, 2 × dose rate
	Neutron	4 × He ₃ tube, 4 × BF ₃ tube, Li Glass, activation foils, 1 × dose rate
	Flow rate	2 × Coriolis, 1 × turbine
	Pressure	5 × piezo pressure detector
	Temperature	11 × PT100 resistance temperature detector

2.1. KATANA experimental campaigns

The KATANA water activation facility at the Jožef Stefan Institute's TRIGA research reactor represents an important step forward in supporting fusion energy research. This innovative facility, which was developed as part of the EUROfusion work package Preparation of ITER Operation (WP PrIO), is used to simulate the behavior of cooling circuits in fusion reactors. By irradiating water for activation and measuring the resulting isotopic composition, researchers gain crucial insights into material behavior and system performance relevant to the ITER operating environment. KATANA enables the investigation of radionuclide production, system calibration techniques and detector performance, bridging the gap between theory and practical application.

Recently, five intensive experimental campaigns took place at the KATANA facility as part of WP PrIO, aimed at addressing the key challenges of water activation in future fusion reactors. More than 30 researchers from ten research groups took part in the campaigns, illustrating the collaborative nature of this ambitious project. On 26 test days, the JSI TRIGA reactor was in operation for more than 200 hours and provided the necessary platform for a variety of tests and measurements. Fifteen experimental measurement systems were deployed, each carefully tailored to collect critical data on water activation under fusion-relevant conditions. The focus of these campaigns was to provide experimental data on the water activation process to validate computational methods developed to model the ITER cooling circuit. In addition, different detectors were used to utilise different measurement techniques for the measurement of mixed high-energy gamma and neutron fields.

Table 2: List of KATANA experimental campaigns.

Name	Time period	Operation	Detectors
Test	26/8/2024 – 30/8/2024	Steady (250kW, long irradiation)	activation foils (In, Au, Ni)
First	21/10/2024 – 25/10/2024	Steady and pulse	HPGe, LaBr, TLD, He3 tubes, Li glass detector
Second	18/11/2024 – 22/11/2024	Steady (250kW, long irradiation)	He3 tubes, Li glass detector, He3 tubes
Third	29/9/2025 – 3/10/2025	Steady (1kW-250kW)	BF3 tubes, He3 tubes, Li glass detector, HPGe, LaBr detector
Fourth	6/10/2025 – 10/10/2025	Steady (250kW, long irradiation)	activation foils (In, Au, Mn, Cd, Ta, Co)

2.2. Measurements

Gamma-ray spectrometry with HPGe and LaBr detectors provides high-resolution spectral data for ^{16}N and ^{19}O decay, quantifying isotope activity and verifying dose-rate predictions used in CFD–neutronics models.

Figure 4. Neutron measurements with activation foils (1 & 2), neutron measurements with Li-glass detectors (3) and gamma-ray measurements with HpGe (4).

Neutron measurements, using calibrated ^3He , ^3BF , and ^6Li glass detectors, characterize both prompt and delayed neutron fluxes from ^{17}N decay. These measurements, supported by neutron activation

method (using the In, Au and Ni activation samples), establish energy-dependent fluence benchmarks for Monte Carlo and CFD coupling validation. Together, the gamma and neutron datasets from JSI enable the validation of isotopic inventories, source strengths, and decay kinetics. This integrated experimental validation ensures that predictive tools for activation and radiation transport in fusion coolant systems are physically grounded and applicable to ITER and DEMO safety assessments.

2.3. Modelling

Modelling is of high importance to the EUROfusion water activation task because it links the measured behaviour of activated coolant to predictive tools that can be applied in ITER, DEMO and other water cooled tokamaks. The activation of cooling water depends on the interplay between neutron fields, fluid dynamics, and radioactive decay – a three-dimensional, transient problem that cannot be solved experimentally alone. Modelling enables the identification of dominant physical mechanisms, optimization of loop geometry, and reliable estimation of radiation dose rates under reactor-relevant conditions. Three complementary teams lead this work. UNED developed FLUNED, an open-source computational fluid dynamic (CFD) –neutronics coupling solver built in OpenFOAM, capable of computing isotope production and decay along complex flow paths. Its strength lies in accessibility and detailed fluid–radiation coupling that supports cross-institutional benchmarking. Also due to code being open it is more accessible. Fusion for Energy (F4E) created the Radio-Species Transport Model (RSTM), implemented in ANSYS Fluent through user-defined scalars. RSTM provides industrial-grade modelling of N-16, N-17, and O-19 transport in three-dimensional reactor geometries. UKAEA developed ActiFlow and GammaFlow, specialized codes that simulate activation kinetics and gamma transport in moving fluids, serving as the reference for cross-code and experimental benchmarking. Ongoing RSTM activities focus on cross-validation with other EUROfusion codes such as FLUNED, ActiFlow, and GammaFlow, and on the benchmarking against experimental data obtained during KATANA campaigns. The RSTM method provides a robust, industrial-grade approach for the prediction of activity build-up, transport, and decay in flowing fluids, supporting safety assessments and the operational readiness of ITER [9,10].

Figure 5. N-16 concentration field solution (at/m³) for JSI KATANA inner irradiation snail head at 0.5 L/s loop operating conditions. Calculated by using the RSTM methodology.

3. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The EUROfusion WP PrIO programme has established the first comprehensive experimental–computational framework for understanding water activation under fusion-relevant conditions. The KATANA activation facility at the JSI TRIGA reactor has proven to be a stable, tunable, and diagnostically rich platform for benchmarking activation models that will be required for ITER operation. Across multiple campaigns, the facility delivered reproducible high-energy gamma and delayed-neutron fields, enabling systematic measurements with HPGe and LaBr spectrometers, Li-glass detectors, ³He/BF₃ systems, activation foils, and TLDs. These measurements confirmed the production and transport of key activation products (¹⁶N, ¹⁷N, ¹⁹O) and provided quantitative dose-rate and flux datasets over varying reactor powers, flow conditions, and irradiation geometries. The

experimental results demonstrate that delayed-neutron emission from ^{17}N and high-energy gamma radiation from ^{16}N can be reliably detected, characterized, and correlated with reactor operating parameters. Parallel modelling efforts by UNED (FLUNED), F4E (RSTM), and UKAEA (ActiFlow/GammaFlow) have reached a mature stage. Each code captures different aspects of the activation-transport problem: open-source CFD-neutronics coupling (FLUNED), industrial-grade 3D activation transport in complex flow fields (RSTM), and reference tools for gamma dose and species transport (ActiFlow/GammaFlow). Overall, the work conducted at KATANA has produced the fusion-relevant benchmark dataset for water activation. Future activities will focus on:

- evaluation of experimental uncertainties
- completing cross-code comparison under all experimental scenarios;
- refining nuclear data for short-lived activation products;
- extending measurements to ITER-relevant flow regimes and irradiation heads;
- performing end-to-end validation of coupled CFD-neutronics-activation tools.

With KATANA now fully operational and validated, the EUROfusion programme has established a unique European capability for understanding and predicting coolant activation phenomena – one that directly supports ITER's operational readiness and the safety assessments of future fusion power plants.

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